

MSME Sector in Uttar Pradesh: Possibility and Policy

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ABSTRACT

Uttar Pradesh is a major state of India in terms of development of small, cottage and medium industries. Uttar Pradesh has maximum number of small, medium and cottage industries as compared to any other state. From the point of view of economic, geographical and human resource, there is immense potential for the development of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh. Every district of Uttar Pradesh is globally famous for a special product. This is the reason that many important steps have been taken by the Uttar Pradesh government keeping in mind the development of the MSME sector. In this context, the "One District One Product Scheme" run by the Government of Uttar Pradesh is most important. Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state of India, so in order to achieve the twin objectives of unemployment prevention and economic development in Uttar Pradesh, it is necessary that the industrial potential of the state of Uttar Pradesh should be given a positive shape.

Keywords: Uttar Pradesh, MSME , One District One Product

AIM OF STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study of the present research paper.

- Throwing light on the development and nature of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh.
- To obtain information about the existing regional industrial specialties in the state of Uttar Pradesh.
- To examine the growth prospects of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh.
- To examine the steps taken by the Government of Uttar Pradesh for the development of MSME sector.

INTRODUCTION

Spread over a wide area from the foothills of the Himalayas to the Ganges Yamuna, Uttar Pradesh has been famous for its handicrafts and artistry since ancient times. This artistry flourished in many small towns and rural areas of India. During the Mughal period, artists from Egypt, Turkey, Afghanistan gave a new dimension to Indian craftsmanship. As a result of this, small and cottage industries developed in the handloom and handicrafts sector on a large scale in Uttar Pradesh. In terms of the total number of MSMEs, Uttar Pradesh ranks first in India, Gujarat is in second place and Madhya Pradesh is in third place. According to the Annual Report-2020-21 of the Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, 90 lakh MSME units were working in Uttar Pradesh, which is 14% of the entire India. The number of MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh has increased rapidly over the years. According to the 4th All India Census of MSMEs, 44.03 lakh units were working in Uttar Pradesh in 2006-07, which was 12 percent of the whole of India. Uttar Pradesh ranks third after Maharashtra and Gujarat in terms of registration related to opening of MSMEs. It is noteworthy that the registration of new enterprises in the MSME sector shows a favorable environment for the MSME sector and the development of entrepreneurship. In terms of employment generation, the MSME sector is second only to agriculture in Uttar Pradesh. A total of 165 lakh people are employed in the MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh, which is the best compared to any other state. The development of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh is also necessary from the point of view of economic empowerment of women. Uttar Pradesh ranks fifth in all India in terms of percentage of women owned MSMEs. Almost all types of industries are working in the MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh is a major state of India in terms of agricultural raw materials. Uttar Pradesh ranks first in total food grain production. The state of Uttar Pradesh also ranks first in the production of fruits. Uttar Pradesh ranks best in the production of important crops like potatoes. Aloe vera, Amla, Ashwagandha, Brahmi etc. are also cultivated in some districts of Uttar Pradesh like Meerut, Saharanpur. This is the reason that the development of agriculture based small and cottage industries is visible on a large scale in Uttar Pradesh. For example, sugar, cotton clothes, vegetable oil, dalda etc. The oldest small and cottage industry of Uttar Pradesh is the handloom industry. Under the handloom industry, cotton cloth, hand woven silk cloth, chikan work, woolen cloth, carpets and rugs, blankets etc. are included. Uttar Pradesh ranks third in the whole of India in cotton textiles. The handloom industry in Uttar Pradesh provides employment to a large

number of people. Banarasi silk sarees of Uttar Pradesh, carpets of Bhadohi, bed cover of Gorakhpur, dari of Sitapur and Etawah, lehenga-chunri of Farukhabad, curtain of Ghazipur, terry-tavel of Ghaziabad are not only well liked in the country but also abroad. Kanpur of Uttar Pradesh is called the Manchester of North India. Along with Kanpur, Bareilly, Agra, Ghaziabad, Meerut, Moradabad, Aligarh are also famous for cotton textile industry. Uttar Pradesh is also very famous for handicrafts made clothes. For example - Chicken of Lucknow, silk sarees of Banaras, Zaridardoji of Rampur etc. There has also been a substantial development of silk industry in Uttar Pradesh. It is noteworthy that India's silk industry is second only to China in the world. Mulberry silk and terry silk are produced in more than 50 districts of Uttar Pradesh. Mirzapur, Sonbhadra, Chandauli, Lakhimpur etc. are the major centers of silk production in Uttar Pradesh. For the development of silk, the Regional Cooperative Sericulture Federation and Silk Research and Development Center are located in Gonda in Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh is also a prominent place from the point of view of leather industry. Districts like Kanpur and Unnao are at a prominent place in India in terms of leather production. Uttar Pradesh ranks first in terms of sugarcane production in the whole of India. This is the reason that there has also been a substantial development of the Khansari industry in Uttar Pradesh. Western Uttar Pradesh's Saharanpur, Meerut, Muzaffarnagar, Bareilly etc. are very famous for Gud and Khandsari industry. Glass industry, paper industry, match industry etc. are important among other units working in MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh. In Uttar Pradesh, Firozabad for glass industry, Saharanpur for paper industry, Moradabad for brass industry, Bareilly for match industry are the major industrial centers.

Uttar Pradesh is one such state in India where each district is famous for some particular product. For example, Bhadohi's carpet, Aligarh's lock, Moradabad's porcelain and brass, Kanpur's leather, Kannauj's perfume etc. Every region of Uttar Pradesh is known for one or the other industrial specialty and artistry. In such a situation, there is immense potential for the development of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh. There is no dearth of demand for goods and services in Uttar Pradesh.

Adequate raw material and labor force is available in Uttar Pradesh, but due to lack of infrastructure and industrial activities, adequate development of entrepreneurship has not been possible here. Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state of India with a population of 20 crores. Therefore, Uttar Pradesh has a strong market in terms of demand for goods and services, which is helpful in encouraging industrial activities here. Due to the huge population, there is no shortage of labor force in Uttar Pradesh. Therefore, sufficient human resources are available for small and cottage industries in Uttar Pradesh. It is noteworthy that the main resource used in the MSME sector is labor. Handmade and artistic items are often produced by small and cottage industries, in which labor is used more. Uttar Pradesh has a prominent place in terms of labor as well as natural resources. Uttar Pradesh has adequate raw material and water resources. Due to simplification of industrial rules, laws and improvement in law and order, a favorable environment is available for investment in Uttar Pradesh. There is also substantial development of transport facilities in Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh has better connectivity in terms of roads than any other state. Therefore, a favorable and encouraging environment exists in Uttar Pradesh towards the MSME sector. According to experts of the Department of Economics and Statistics, today Uttar Pradesh has become the state with the second largest economy in the country. Now Uttar Pradesh is moving towards becoming a one trillion economy state. At present the size of the economy of the Uttar Pradesh is \$230 billion. In the last few years, many important steps have been taken for the development of MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh. In recent years the following important steps have been taken by the Government of Uttar Pradesh for the development of MSME sector.

A major problem before small and cottage industries is related to finance. Differentiated behavior is often done by big banks with small and cottage industries. The enthusiasm with which India's big nationalized and private sector banks give loans to big industries is not seen in relation to small and cottage industries. Small and cottage industries often do not even have anything to mortgage. Therefore, it is not easy for them to get loans from banks. The Government of Uttar Pradesh has taken several steps to deal with this situation. Several steps have been taken by the Uttar Pradesh government to provide collateral free loans to the MSME sector. Under the self-reliant India scheme announced by the Prime Minister of India, there has been talk of providing collateral free loans up to 3 lakh to the MSME sector. Uttar Pradesh Principal Secretary Rajendra Kumar Tiwari has said that in the last four and a half years, the Uttar Pradesh government has provided employment opportunities to more than 1.50 crore people by providing loans to about 80 lakh micro, small and medium scale industrial units. A total of 89.99 lakh units are registered in the state, which is 14.20 percent of the total registered units of the country. Online loan fair is being organized by the state government to provide maximum loan to the MSME sector through banks. While Rs 28,136 crore was disbursed as loan to MSMEs in 2016-17, Rs 73,765 crore was disbursed in the year 2020-21, which shows a growth of more than two and a half times in the last four and a half years. In the financial year 2020-21, more than 63 lakh people have been provided employment by disbursing loans to 34,80,596 new MSME units through various schemes. State's exports increased by 35 percent from the year 2017-18 to 2020-21. In order to increase livelihood opportunities and accelerate business activities in the economic conditions arising out of Covid-19, the Government of Uttar Pradesh has disbursed adequate loan to the MSME sector. This will also help in increasing the purchasing power of the people, which will increase the demand for goods and services in the state. MSME Saathi Portal

and Mobile App have been launched to provide loans to the MSME sector on adequate and easy terms. The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) online loan fair has been launched by the Uttar Pradesh government. This loan is given by the government through those banks with which the state government has tied up. This loan fair organized by the Government of Uttar Pradesh will help in increasing the number of MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh. Within 24 hours, the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh gave a one-time loan of more than 2000 to 56 thousand entrepreneurs of the MSME sector of the state, under the economic package released by the Central Government under the Self-Reliant India Scheme. Immediately after the announcement of the economic package by the Central Government, Uttar Pradesh has become the first state to give loan of such a huge amount in the lockdown.

Several efforts have been made by the Government of Uttar Pradesh to provide the necessary conducive environment for the development of the MSME sector. The investment climate of the state has improved significantly due to the efforts of the government. Several important steps have been taken by the government towards simplification of rules and regulations for the MSME sector. The rules for all types of NOCs along with environment have been simplified for the newly emerging small enterprises. All these certificates for transparency will be available in a stipulated time through single window system. According to the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh, entrepreneurs setting up units in the MSME sector will be able to apply for a no-objection in the last 100 days of 1000 days. The entrepreneur setting up the unit will get loan from the bank on easy terms. For this, a huge loan fair will be organized in every district from May 12 to 20. In the meeting of the State Level Bankers Committee, instructions have been given to the banks in this regard. The Chief Minister said that more and more entrepreneurs should be encouraged to set up units of micro, small and medium industries in the state and a detailed action plan should be prepared for this. Taking a big step to remove red tape in the establishment of MSME industries, the Yogi government has approved the "Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Establishment and Operation) Act-2020" through cabinet bicirculation on August 18. Under this new act, it is being arranged that the acceptance certificate will be issued within 72 hours after the entrepreneur submits the prescribed form in the District Industries Center. After the issue of this certificate, the unit will not require any permission from any government department for 900 days and can start its enterprise immediately. According to Uttar Pradesh Principal Secretary Navneet Sehgal, a target has been set to provide 5 lakh new jobs in a year through the new Act. There is a provision of Facilitation Council to resolve matters between private units and MSME department. At present, due to having only one Facilitation Council, there are many pending cases of MSMEs. In the new Act, it is proposed to set up a Facilitation Council at the Mandal level. With this, the problems of MSMEs at the divisional level will be resolved on priority in the Facilitation Council headed by the Divisional Commissioner. It is noteworthy that due to the improvement in the industrial environment, Uttar Pradesh has been ranked second in the 'Ease of Doing Business' rank.

Along with removing the responsive constraints, several important steps have also been taken to provide necessary infrastructure related facilities to the MSME sector. like -

1. Under the Uttar Pradesh Export Infrastructure Development Scheme, a modern testing lab has been set up on the Agra-Mathura highway for testing leather products. Earlier, entrepreneurs depended on labs in France and Germany for testing leather products.
2. Modern foreign machines have been installed by the Department of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) for the finishing of handicraft buttons made from buffalo horn in Sambhal.
3. MSME parks are being set up by the Government of Uttar Pradesh. Two Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) parks are being constructed in New Okhla Industrial Development Authority (Noida) area of Gautam Buddha Nagar district. The Yamuna Expressway Industrial Development Authority is developing these parks as a model to boost the MSME sector by helping globalize indigenous products. After MSME parks in Noida, similar parks will be set up in Agra, Kanpur, Moradabad, Varanasi, Azamgarh and Gorakhpur, which will have many MSMEs. Such MSME parks will usher in a new era in the industrial development of Uttar Pradesh. Besides the factory, MSME Park will have facilities like business centre, shopping centre, incubation centre, hotel and restaurant, hostel, office block, health and fire station. The parks will also be provided by the government with excellent roads, electricity, water supply network, storehouses, container and truck terminals, railway siding infrastructure and fuel stations.
4. Pottery wheels, bee boxes, agarbatti making machines were distributed in Bundelkhand region by the Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Major programs like PMEGP, Honey Mission and Kumhar Sashaktikaran Mission have been run by the government in this area.
5. Flatted factory is being set up in Prayagraj district to promote cottage industries.

Keeping in mind the development of MSME sector, the following programs have been run by the Government of Uttar Pradesh.

1 - **MUKHYAMANTREE YUVA SVAROJAGAAR YOJANA:** The purpose of this scheme is to motivate the young workers of Uttar Pradesh for self-employment. Under this scheme, a loan of up to ₹ 25000 is given for self-employment. The loan limit for service sector is up to ₹ 1000000.

2 - **ONE DISTRICT ONE PRODUCT SCHEME:** In fact, the "One District - One Product" scheme is a part of the strategy of "Local to Global" of self-reliant India plan. Under this scheme, first of all the products will be identified at the local level, after that necessary steps will be taken by the government for the production and marketing of these items. Like makhana in Bihar, mango in UP, ragi in Karnataka, turmeric in Telangana, saffron in Kashmir and bamboo and herbal products in North East are famous, similarly under the "One District - One Product" scheme, MSMEs based on local products will be established in every region of Uttar Pradesh. The government will cooperate in the establishment, management and operation of these industries. Under the "One District One Product" scheme, a particular product will be selected in each district. Under the very ambitious One District One Product" scheme by the Government of Uttar Pradesh, such items produced at the local level will be identified which have a unique identity in the country and abroad and which can be given special GI tag or geographical identification mark, such as - Nutritious Black salt rice, Chikankari, Zari-Zardozi and embroidery work on clothes, very intricate craft work from horns and bones of dead animals, artistic specimens on ivory, marble, sandalwood etc., carvings on various metals and other handicrafts.

3 - **ONE DISTRICT ONE PRODUCT MARGIN MONEY SCHEME:** Under this scheme, 20% of the project cost under the "One District One Product" scheme will be financed by the government, which will be maximum 50 lakhs or maximum 6.25 lakhs. To apply under the scheme, one should be a permanent citizen of the state of UP and the age of the applicant should be between 18-40 years.

4 - **VISHVAKARMA SHRAM SAMMAAN YOJANA:** Under this scheme, potters, weavers, carpenters, blacksmiths, barbers etc. are trained to encourage new technology based skill development. Under this scheme, 250 people are trained in 6 days training.

5 - **ONE DISTRICT ONE PRODUCT TRAINING AND TOOL-KIT SCHEME:** Through this scheme, skilled people are given training under RPL as well as certificates. Under this scheme, unskilled persons will be given training for ten days and will also get a reward of Rs 200 each day during the coaching session.

- The Uttar Pradesh government has approved the establishment of an MSME park in the state, under which the state's first MSME park is being set up in Sector 29 and 32 of Yamuna Expressway Development Authority (YIDA). Apart from this, soon similar parks will be set up in Agra, Kanpur, Moradabad, Varanasi, Azamgarh and Gorakhpur. Large number of MSME units are functioning in these six districts.
- During the Covid-19 lockdown, skill mapping and scaling of workers and laborers coming back to their homes in Uttar Pradesh from other states were done so that they could be provided employment in the MSME sector as per their qualifications. About 15 lakh workers were trained by the Uttar Pradesh government by conducting skill mapping so that they could be provided employment in the MSME sector. According to the report of the Reserve Bank of India, the state of Uttar Pradesh ranked 5th in relation to providing employment to migrant laborers in micro, small and medium industries (MSMEs) during the Corona crisis. The Reserve Bank of India has prepared a report of employment in the MSME sector after assessing all the states of the country. States like Rajasthan, Karnataka, Delhi and Punjab lag behind Uttar Pradesh in terms of employment generation through MSMEs. After Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat and Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh was ranked 5th in terms of employment generation during the Corona crisis in RBI's ranking. The Uttar Pradesh government played an important role in providing employment to more than 40 lakh migrant laborers trapped in other states during the Corona crisis. The highly ambitious "One District one Product" (ODOP) scheme run by the Uttar Pradesh government has emerged as a game changer in relation to employment generation during the Corona crisis. Under ODOP, products from 75 districts are being sold nationally and internationally on online platforms like Amazon and Flipkart. Small districts like Etah, Pilibhit, Mirzapur and Pratapgarh in Uttar Pradesh have become employment hubs due to successful implementation of ODOP.
- Several steps have been taken by the Uttar Pradesh government to promote research and innovation in the MSME sector. The MSME Department of Uttar Pradesh has signed an MOU with "APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University" (AKTU). Students of 756 colleges affiliated to the university will work towards promoting innovation, incubation and self-employment by joining the ODOP scheme.

- It was ordered by the Uttar Pradesh government in March last year that every department would procure 25 percent of its annual budget from the MSME sector. This policy has yielded very positive results. In the current financial year till November 10, the government procurement from MSEs through GEM portal has been 69.6 percent i.e. 3855 crore. In the last four and a half years, this purchase has been done for more than 15 thousand crores.
- The Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises has announced to include retail and wholesale trade under MSME. This will benefit lakhs of wholesale and retail traders of Uttar Pradesh. They will also get the loan earmarked for the MSME sector.

Certainly, with the above mentioned policy efforts, a conducive and positive environment will be created for the MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh, which will encourage entrepreneurship in Uttar Pradesh. At present, a major problem in front of small and cottage industries is competition from domestic industries and multinational companies. In terms of management, finance and technology, the MSME sector is not impressive enough to compete with large industries and multinational companies. In terms of raw materials too, there is often competition between large industries and the MSME sector. In this situation, it is necessary that a conducive policy framework towards the MSME sector in Uttar Pradesh should be formulated. At the same time, efforts should be made to connect the MSME sector with the market economy and new technology. Foreign investment should be invited in the MSME sector. Small and cottage industries should be established in rural and semi-urban areas near raw materials so that they can meet the local demand. The start-up and stand-up policy run by the Uttar Pradesh government should be given wide publicity in rural and semi-urban areas. Efforts should be made to encourage self-employment and self-business. One member of each family should be motivated for small-business by linking it to the start-up policy. Only by following these things, we can make the MSME sector helpful in the economic development of Uttar Pradesh and can fulfill the dream of rapid economic development in Uttar Pradesh with unemployment prevention.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in all respects, a favorable environment is available for small and cottage industries in Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh is in a stronger position than any other state in terms of labor force, natural resources, raw materials, roads and transport. Every region of Uttar Pradesh is associated with some economic and commercial specialty. What is needed is that it be made a reality. In recent years, several important steps have been taken by the Government of Uttar Pradesh for the accelerated development of the MSME sector. "One District One Product" Scheme is an important step in this regard. To transform the economy of Uttar Pradesh into a 1 trillion dollar economy, it is necessary that emphasis should be given on the development of MSME sector. For this, emphasis should be laid on improving the industrial environment as well as infrastructure related facilities. Along with the training of employees working in the MSME sector, finance, technical and managerial facilities should also be provided to the MSME sector.

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